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Research Article

**COMPARATIVE STUDY OF *IN-VITRO* ANTIOXIDANT
ACTIVITY ON DIFFERENT FRUIT PEELS****Kolupula Ramprasad*, N. Lalitha, Zainab Firdows, Iram Saba, Sana Afreen,
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LMD Colony, Thimmapur, Karimnagar.**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

The objective of the investigations performed was to evaluate the peels of selected fruits for some nutritional and anti-nutritional components including Carbohydrates, Protein, Antioxidants, Protease and Tannin. Sundried and finely ground fruit peels are subjected to various reactions in order to estimate the quantities of each of the desired components. In the results accomplished, highest carbohydrate content was found in Pomegranate (55.2 mg/ml) followed by Apple (37.15) and Orange (32.64 mg/ml) and Kiwi (22.7mg/ml). Highest protein concentrations were observed in Kiwi (1.6mg/ml) followed by Orange fruit (1.33 mg/ml), Pomegranate (1.06 mg/ml) and Apple (1.06 mg/ml). Highest antioxidant activity was noted in Pomegranate (0.57%) followed by Orange (0.53%), Apple (0.47%). High Protease concentrations were noted in Pomegranate (1.06 mg/ml) followed by Apple (0.3 mg/ml). Highest Tannin content was observed in Apple and Pomegranate (42.46 µg/ml) followed by Watermelon (35.72 µg/ml).

Keywords: Antioxidant activity, fruit peels, carbohydrates, protein, protease, tannin.

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INTRODUCTION:

Numerous scientific investigations point at consecutive rich sources of anti microbes, especially among fruits peels, but few of them involve waste parts of fruits, i.e., seeds n peels. Many of the fruit's skins are thrown in garbage or fed to livestock. These are having a very rich bio active compounds which are considered to have beneficial effects on health to health. In the present investigation, the antioxidant properties of peels of different fruits, that are commonly available and readily consumed in India.

Undoubtedly, fruit skin comprises the highest percentage of waste in most kitchen bins. This is not something to be shocked about, especially if the members in the household cook their food at home. However it can be shocking at times that people are not yet knowledgeable on the proper means of recycling and reusing peels. While you can eat some of them a lot of peels are actually beneficial when it comes to the home sanitary purposes. But wait, peels aren't all about cleaning the house they are more than that. Here are is a list of some of the most beneficial uses of fruits peels.

Fruit peel, or fruit skin is the outer, protective covering in fruits. In general, the skin in some tough-layered fruits such as pomegranate, etc., is known as the rind, while in citrus fruits such as in oranges, it is better termed as peel. Besides its outer cover protect underlying edible portion of fruit from harsh environmental factors as well as micro and macro organisms. It indeed, holds some of vital health benefiting constituents such as dietary fibre, and phyto-nutrients that help accomplish overall wellness.

The peel of an orange packs in twice as much vitamin C as what's inside. It also contains higher concentrations of riboflavin, vitamin B₆, calcium, magnesium and potassium. The peel's flavonoids have anti-cancer and anti-inflammatory property. (Citrus fruit also boosts iron absorption). The entire peel is bitter and difficult to digest. Instead, grate the peel using a micro plane or another tool and sprinkle it on top of salads, or in a vinaigrette dressing. Citrus shavings make a good pairing with ice cream and chocolate as well^{1,2}.

PLANT PROFILE:**Table: (i) Indicates Apple**

Kingdom	Plantae
Order	Rosales
Family	Rosaceae
Genus	Malus
Species	M. domestica
Binomial name: Malus Domestica Borkh	
Synonyms: Malus common Dest, Malus pumila Mil, Pyrus malus Var paradisiacal L.	

COMMON NAMES:

Saeb (Hindi), Seena regi pandu (Telugu), Narankaai (Tamil), Sebu (Kannada), Safarjan (Gujarati).

USES:

- Apples are used to control diarrhoea/constipation.
- They prevent lung cancer, fights asthma.
- It treats vit-c deficiency condition called scurvy^{3,4}.

Table (ii) Indicates Kiwi

Kingdom	Plantae
Order	Ericales
Family	Actinidiaceae
Genus	Actinidia
Species	A. deliciosa
Binomial name: Actinidia Deliciosa	
Synonyms: Chinese gooseberry, woody vine	

COMMON NAMES:

Kevee (Hindi), Kivi pandu (Telugu), Kivi phala (Gujarati).

USES:

- Helps to treat asthma.
- Aids digestion.
- Boosts immune system.
- Manages blood pressure.
- Reduces blood clotting⁵.

Table (iii) Indicates Orange

Kingdom	Plantae
Order	Sapindates
Family	Rutaceae
Genus	Citrus. L
Species	C. sinensis
Binomial name :Citrus Sinensis (L)	
Synonyms : Apricot, Tangerine, Peach, Sour-orange, Titian, Coral	

COMMON NAMES:

Santra (Hindi), Kamala pandu (Telugu), Kesari phala (Marathi), Narangi phala (Gujarati)

USES:

- Oranges are excellent source of vit-c
- Prevents skin damage.
- Lowers cholesterol.
- Lower risk of cancer^{6,7,8,9}.

Table (iv) Indicates pomegranate

Kingdom	Plantae
Order	Myrtales
Family	Lythraceae
Genus	Punica
Species	P. granatum
Binomial name :Punica granatum L	
Synonyms: Punica florida salisb, Punica nana L, Punica grandiflora hortex sterd,Punica spinosa Lam.	

COMMON NAMES:

Anar (Hindi), Dalimb (Marathi), Dalima pandu (Telugu), Madulai (Tamil).

USES:

- Pomegranate juice helpful to treat erectile dysfunction
- Pomegranate lowers B.P.
- Useful against breast cancer^{10,11,12,13}.

Table (v) Indicates Watermelon

Kingdom	Plantae
Order	Cucurbit tales
Family	Cucurbitaceae
Genus	Citrullus
Species	C. Lanatus
Binomial name : Citrullus Lanatus(thumb) Matsum & Nakai	
Synonyms :Melon, watermelon Vine, Citrullus Vulgaris	

COMMON NAMES:

Tarabuja (Hindi), Puccakaya (Telugu), Tarabuja (Marathi), Taramuja (Bengali).

USES:

- Helps in body hydration.
- Lowers inflammation & oxidative stress.
- Helps to prevent macular degeneration
- Improves digestion¹⁴.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collected fruits were washed, peeled and their peels were carefully separated removing any amount of edible portions. The peels were air dried for 1 week and then ground to fine powder. Powdered samples were kept in airtight bags under refrigeration during the study period. Standard

procedures followed for estimation of various contents in the fruit peels are displayed in table 1¹⁵.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

When the fruit peels were analyzed for carbohydrate content, highest concentrations were found in Pomegranate (55.2 mg/ml), Apple (37.15 mg/ml), Orange (32.64mg/ml) and Kiwi (22.7mg/ml). Least concentration was found in watermelon (8.81 mg/ml). The result shows significant amount of carbohydrates in the fruit peels and hence they can be utilized as a source of carbohydrates. Carbohydrate concentration was also seen highest in Pomegranate peels in the studies of Rowayshed *et al.* (2013). Kiwi and Orange peels also contain significant amounts of carbohydrates as estimated by

Table 1: Estimation of various components in fruit peels using standard procedures

Components analysed	Method	Procedure	Estimation
Carbohydrates	Anthrone method (Roe J.H, 1955)	1g each of 10 powdered peel samples were weighed and filtered then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. Supernatant was made up to a volume of 30 mL. Then 4 mL-1 of Anthrone reagent was added and kept in a boiling water bath for 10 minutes ^{16,17,18} .	Supernatant was rapidly cooled and provided the dark green color at 620 nm using a spectrophotometer. Total carbohydrate content was then calculated using the obtained absorbance values of samples and standard.
Protein	FolinLowry's method (Lowry <i>et al.</i> , 1951)	Samples were mixed thoroughly with 7 ml phosphate buffer and filtered out using cheese cloth. Filtrate was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes. Supernatant was made up to 10 ml using buffer. 1 ml of 10% TCA was added to one mL of the solution and shaken thoroughly. It was then kept in freezer for 15 minutes. Centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes and upper layer was decanted. Pellet is taken and dissolved in 0.1N NaOH. 0.1 ml aliquot was taken and made up to 1 ml using 0.1N NaOH. 5 ml alkaline copper reagent was added and kept for 10 minutes. Then 0.5 ml of reagent D (1ml Folin's reagent + 1 ml 0.1 N NaOH) was added and the solution was kept for 30 minutes ¹⁹ .	Resultant blue color was read at 670 nm using a spectrophotometer. Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) solution (20-100 Mg/ml) was used as standard. Protein concentration was calculated by applying test and standard values in the corresponding equation.
Antioxidant	Reducing power assay method (Yen GC and Duh PD; 1994)	1 g each of powdered samples was extracted using 10 ml distilled water, then 2.5mL phosphate buffer (0.2M, pH 6.6) and 2.5mL potassium ferri cyanide was added. To this 2.5mL of trichloroacetic acid (100g/L) was added, and centrifuged at 3000rpm for 10 minutes, then the mixture was incubated at 50°C for 20 minutes. Finally, 2.5mL of the supernatant was mixed with 2.5mL of distilled water and 0.5mL FeCl ₃ (1g/L) ^{20,21} .	The absorbance was measured at 700nm in UV- Visible Spectrophotometer. Ascorbic acid was used as standard and phosphate buffer as blank solution.
Tannin	Vanillin Hydrochloride method (Robert, E B;	1g each of ground sample was extracted with 50 ml methanol. After 24 hours Centrifuged and to 1 ml of supernatant 5 ml of vanillin hydrochloride reagent was added ²² .	Read in a spectrophotometer at 500 nm after 20 minutes. Blank was set with vanillin hydrochloride reagent alone. A

	1971		standard graph with 20-100 μg catechin was prepared using the diluted stock solution (1 mg catechin/ml).
Protease	Anson, M.L., 1938	1 g each of samples was extracted in 10 ml distilled water ,centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes. 0.5 ml of the aliquot again incubated for 30 minutes with 1 ml 2% casein in 0.1M Tris- HCl buffer at 37oC for 10 minutes. Reaction was stopped by adding 5 ml 5% TCA and incubated for 30 minutes. To the filtrate 4 ml 0.1N NaOH and 0.5 ml Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added ²³ .	Amount of tyrosine released was measured at 670 nm using a spectrophotometer

Figure 1: Graph of showing concentration of carbohydrate in different fruit peels

Anhwange et al. (2009) and Osarumwense et al. (2013), respectively (Figure 1).When the fruit peels were analyzed for carbohydrate content, highest concentrations were found in followed by Pomegranate (55.2 mg/ml), Apple (37.15 mg/ml), Orange (32.64 mg/ml) and Kiwi (22.7mg/ml). Least concentration was found in Watermelon (8.81 mg/ml). The result shows significant amount of carbohydrates in the fruit peels and hence they can be utilized as a source of carbohydrates. Carbohydrate concentration was also seen highest in Pomegranate peels in the studies of Rowayshed et al. (2013). Kiwi and Orange peels also contain significant amounts of carbohydrates as estimated by Anhwange et al. (2009) and Osarumwense et al. (2013) respectively.

Figure 2: Graph showing concentration of Protein in various fruit peels

On estimation, highest protein concentration was found in Kiwi (1.6 mg/ ml) followed by Orange fruit (1.33 mg/ml), Pomegranate (1.06 mg/ml) and Apple (1.06 mg/ml). So, findings of this study suggest that Kiwi can be highly recommended for daily consumption or usage in the diet owing to its high protein content. Least amounts were found in watermelon (0.16 mg/ml). The result agrees with Saranya et al. (2013) about high concentrations of protein in Kiwi, Orange and Pomegranate and low amounts in watermelon (Figure 2). The results show that significant amounts of protein are present in various fruit peels and their proper and economical recycling can lead to many economical protein containing products.

Figure 3: Graph showing percentage concentration of antioxidants in different fruit peels

Antioxidant activity of different fruit peels were analyzed by estimating their reducing power percentage in this study. Pomegranate showed the maximum level (0.57 %) of antioxidants followed by Orange (0.53 %), Kiwi (0.5 %) and Apple (0.47 %). Least amounts were found in Watermelon (0.03 %) (Figure 3). As earlier studies show that food with high anti-oxidant properties will have great potential to fight or curb many degenerative diseases, in this context it can be recommended that both pomegranates are vital sources of antioxidant components and thereby should be included in our daily consumption. The result of this study is in accordance with Saranya et al. (2013) which also revealed high antioxidant concentration and activity in Pomegranate, Orange and Kiwi. In a study conducted by Kim (2013) fruits were ranked according to their antioxidant capacity as pomegranate>orange>kiwi>apple>watermelon. The ranking of the fruits based on their antioxidant activity in the present investigation is similar with their observation. The differences in the antioxidant activities among the fruits could be attributed to their differences in phenolic contents and compositions and to other non-phenolic antioxidants present in the samples (Wolfe et al. 2003). The probable reason for low antioxidant capacity observed in the present investigation compared to available values in the literature may be (i) low quality of the grape fruits available in the local market, (ii) long period of transportation from the place of production to the market (iii) geographical differences and (iv) difference in variety of the fruits.

Figure 4: Graph showing concentration of Protease in different fruit peels.

The result obtained does not comply with results of Saranya et al. (2013). As here Pomegranate (1.06mg/ml) is found to have highest amount of protease activity rather than Kiwi (0.1mg/ml) in the aforementioned report and apple is found to have more protease concentration than estimated (Figure 4).

Figure 5: Graph showing concentration of Tannin in various fruit peels.

Highest concentration of Tannin was found in Apple and Pomegranate (42.46 µg/ml) followed by watermelon (35.72 µg/ml). Least amount was found in Kiwi fruit (1.43 µg/ml) (Figure 5). The result complies with that of Duda-Chodak et al; 2007 about high concentrations of tannins in watermelon and apple and low quantities in Orange. Pomegranate peels have been attested as an important source of Tannins by Saad et al. (2012). Tannins constitute an essential fraction in the peels of fruits. In many cases, the fruit peels are the waste products of technological processes. These results showed that extracted tannic acid from peel sources can be used as preservation material in food processing and component of cosmetic materials and pharmacological drugs and as an antioxidant source. This could bring measurable economical profits.

CONCLUSION:

Peels are the major by-products obtained during the processing of various fruits. Present study shows that these are good sources of many bioactive components which possess various beneficial effects on human health. But there are anti-nutritional factors also which can have adverse effects and reduce the nutritional quality but they are less in amount compared to the nutritional factors. The study on fruit peels can be helpful in understanding the nature of various components and their levels in different fruit peels provide insights on better usage of fruit wastes. Thus, we may conclude that peels of several fruits are effective resource of antioxidants which can be effectively utilized in food, pharmaceutical and agricultural industries. Further studies on the identification, isolation, characterization and elucidation of structure of the bioactive compounds can help in utilizing the valuable nutrients in fruit peels instead of wasting them.

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